

Extractive Method of Separation of Cadmium(II) as Ethylxanthate from a Number of Ions in Solutions of Binary Mixtures

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Manuscript received 6 January 1993, revised 22 February 1993, accepted 4 May 1993

Similar to zinc¹, cadmium forms ethylxanthate complex (1 : 2) which is completely extractable in chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. Details of its solitary extraction behaviour has been reported earlier². The purpose of this communication is to report our recently developed extractive method of quantitative separation of Cd^{II} from a number of ions which being present in aqueous solutions of binary mixtures cause interference during the quantitative estimation of it through extraction as its ethylxanthate in CCl₄, reextraction with suitable reagent and titration complexometrically.

The effect of various cations and anions on a single extraction of cadmium as ethylxanthate under the conditions of general procedure² (pH 4-11, 2-3 drops of pyridine, equal volumes of extractant and aqueous solutions shaking for 2 min) have been examined. The distribution constant value of cadmium, $K_d = [\text{Cd-Et-xanthate in CCl}_4] / [\text{Cd}^{2+} \text{ in aqueous phase}]$, at pH ~ 6 and at room temperature (~25°), has been found to be

1.3×10^3 . It is seen that Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Sn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Bi^{III}, Fe^{III}, As^{III}, Sb^{III}, UO₂^{II}, VO₃⁻ and EDTA²⁻ interfere in the Cd-xanthate system either through co-extraction or through co-stripping or in co-titration. Alkali and alkaline earth metals, tartrate, HF₂⁻, CrO₄²⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, SO₄²⁻, I⁻, citrate and oxalate do not interfere.

Depending upon the nature of interference, the simple extractive method of quantitative separation of Cd^{II} (>98%) from the above interfering ions are concisely described in Table 1. Whether a single procedure can be adopted for a wide range of concentration ratios has also been tested. This is illustrated with binary mixtures of Cd^{II} with Pb^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}. In these descriptions unless otherwise mentioned, the 'reagent' is the aqueous solution (4-5 ml) of 1% potassium ethyl-xanthate, the 'extractant' is CCl₄ with 2-4 drops of pyridine, the immiscible phases are of equal volume (20 ml), the stripping solution is HNO₃ (~0.3 N), and the shaking rate is 2 strokes per second.

TABLE I—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF CADMIUM FROM THE INTERFERING IONS IN BINARY MIXTURES

Mixture (mg ratio) separated	Procedure
Cd ^{II} : Zn ^{II} (4.5 : 50)	The binary mixtures is treated successively with 2 ml Na-acetate solution (48 g dm ⁻³), 10 ml buffer of pH~10 (NH ₃ /NH ₄ Cl), reagent and extractant, and then shaken (150 strokes). Zn retains in aqueous phase. Cd is transferred to organic phase. It is then stripped. Much excess Xn ⁻ may co-extract some Zn as well. Zn may also be separated by stripping method after simultaneous extraction with Cd (Ref. 1).
Cd ^{II} : Pb ^{II} (1 : 17), (26 : 0.5)	pH of the mixture is adjusted to 6-7 (KAc/HAc or NH ₄ Ac). The reagent and the extractant are then successively added and shaken (150 strokes). Both are extracted. Depending upon the lead content, the organic phase is treated with one or more portions of 0.05-0.07N HCl and 3-12 drops 2% Xn ⁻ solution and shaken (200 strokes). Cd goes to the HCl phase and Pb is retained in organic phase. Pb is stripped with 0.5-3.0N HNO ₃ .

Cd ^{II} : Hg ^{II} (HCl, HNO ₃) (1 : 25)	The mixture is adjusted to 0.08–0.1 <i>N</i> with respect to the acid. More than one extraction operations consecutively with 2% Xn ⁻ solution (7 ml and 3 ml) and extractant (with 400 and 300 strokes respectively) extract both. Cd is stripped with HNO ₃ (0.25 <i>N</i>). Hg is retained in organic phase.
Cd ^{II} : Bi ^{III} (5 <i>N</i> HNO ₃) (5 : 25)	Acidity of the mixture is reduced to pH~2 (NH ₄ OH). 2% Xn ⁻ solution and extractant are successively added and shaken. Both are extracted. Cd is stripped (0.3 <i>N</i> HNO ₃ , 250-300 strokes). Bi is retained in organic phase. Alternately : The acidity of mixture is adjusted to 0.8 to 1 <i>N</i> by partial neutralisation with ammonia, then treated successively with somewhat excess of Xn ⁻ solution (2% ; 10 ml) and the extractant, then shaken (60–70 strokes, before shaking 1 ml 5 <i>N</i> HNO ₃ is added). Only Bi is extracted in organic phase leaving Cd in aqueous solution.
Cd ^{II} : As ^{III} (5 : 25)	The pH of mixture is adjusted to 5–6 (KAc/HAc). Successively reagent and extractant are added and shaken. Both are extracted. Cd is stripped. As is retained in organic phase.
Cd ^{II} : Sb ^{III} ^a (5 : 62)	The mixture is first treated with K-H-tartrate (~62 mg). Its acidity is then reduced with ~2 <i>N</i> KOH and the pH adjusted to ~ 5 (KAc/HAc). 3% Xn ⁻ solution (7 ml) and extractant are added and shaken. Both are extracted. Cd is stripped from organic phase using 0.5 <i>N</i> HNO ₃ . 0.3% of the total Sb co-strips. A repetition of the extraction and stripping operations with the first acid stripping, right from the reduction of acidity etc. in order and using less quantity of Xn ⁻ (4–5 ml; 3%) leaves all Sb in organic phase.
Cd ^{II} : Sn ^{II} (1 <i>N</i> HCl) ^b (5 : 25)	The acidity of mixture is first reduced (NaOH, ~ 1 <i>N</i>) and adjusted to a pH~5.5 (KAc/HAc). Sufficient KNO ₃ (to avoid emulsion formation), Xn ⁻ solution (5 ml, 2%) and the extractant are then added and shaken (150–200 strokes). Both are extracted Cd is stripped. Sn is retained in organic phase.
Cd ^{II} : Fe ^{III} (4.5 : 5), (4.5 : 0.05)	The pH of mixture is adjusted to ~4 (KAc/HAc). The reagent and extractant are successively added and shaken. Both are extracted. Cd is stripped. Fe is retained in organic phase as brown solution of Fe ^{III} -xanthate.
Cd ^{II} : Co ^{II} ^c (5 : 2), (5 : 10)	The pH of mixture is adjusted to ~7.5 (NH ₃ /NH ₄ Cl). Na-citrate (~15 mg) is added to overcome the scum formation. 2% Xn ⁻ solution (5 ml) and extractant are then added and shaken. Both are extracted. Cd is stripped. Co is retained in organic phase. Recovery of Cd is 100% when Cd : Co ratio is 5 : 2.
Cd ^{II} : Cu ^{II} ^d (5 : 25), (21 : 1)	The pH of mixture is adjusted to 4.5–6 (KAc/HAc). The reagent and the extractant are added, shaken and the layers are separated. Depending upon the quantity of Cu several such extractions, each accompanying Xn ⁻ solution, are necessary. Both are extracted. A pinch of thiourea helps the extraction of yellow-brown Cu-xanthate. Cd is stripped (0.1–0.2 <i>N</i> HNO ₃). Cu is retained in organic phase. On standing the organic layer turns green.
Cd ^{II} : Ni ^{II} ^e (5 : 10.7)	The pH of mixture is adjusted to ~5 (KAc/HAc). 2% Xn ⁻ solution (7 ml) and extractant are added and shaken. Both are extracted. Cd is stripped with 0.1 <i>N</i> HNO ₃ . Ni is co-stripped (13% of the total). Ni is removed from the acid-strip as dimethylglyoxime complex through a second extraction with DMG in chloroform. Alternatively : The acidity of the first acid-strip (0.1 <i>N</i>) is reduced (KOH), pH adjusted to ~7.5 (NH ₄ Ac/NH ₃). Xn ⁻ solution and extractant are added and shaken. Both are extracted. Cd is stripped (0.1 <i>N</i> HNO ₃). Repetition of two such extraction and stripping operations, each with the acid-strip of the earlier operation, removes Ni from the third acid-strip retaining only Cd.
Cd ^{II} : UO ₂ ^{II} (5 : 25)	The pH of mixture is adjusted to ~7 (NH ₄ Ac/NH ₃). The reagent and the extractant are added and shaken. Both are extracted. Cd is stripped from organic layer, UO ₂ ²⁺ is retained in organic phase.
Cd ^{II} : EDTA ²⁻ ^f (5 : 10)	The pH of mixture is adjusted to ~5.5 (NaAc/HAc). 2% Xn ⁻ solution (5 ml), Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ (2 g) and extractant are added and shaken. Only Cd is extracted. It is stripped. EDTA is retained in aqueous phase.
Cd ^{II} : VO ₃ ⁻ ^g (HNO ₃ , 0.8 <i>N</i>) (5 : 30)	The acidity of mixture is reduced (KOH) and pH is adjusted to ~5 (KAc/HAc). 2% Xn ⁻ solution (5 ml) and extractant are added and shaken. Only Cd is extracted; it is stripped. VO ₃ ⁻ is retained in aqueous phase.

^aAntimony in the acid-strip is detected (Rhodamine B) and estimated iodometrically.

^bSn^{II} is co-extracted and forms an emulsion. KNO₃ dispels emulsion formation.

^cCo^{II} is co-extracted and forms a scum at the interface. Na-citrate (15 mg) helps to overcome the scum formation for low Co content (5 : 2). For higher Co content (5 : 10), 15 mg Na-citrate cannot prevent scum formation completely. The scum at the interface hinders Cd extraction.

^dCu forms a scum at the interface and is also co-extracted. When Cu content is low (21 : 1), several extractions each with less quantity of xanthate, extract both completely. With higher Cu (5 : 25) content, Cd is mainly extracted leaving some Cu in the scum. Large excess of Cu hinders Cd extraction.

^eNi^{II} in the acid-strip is detected by DMG and is removed as DMG complex in CHCl₃. NH₄OH is added until turbidity appears, minimum quantity of 1% citric acid or Na-citrate solution is added to clarify it, then 2 ml 1% DMG and CHCl₃ are added and shaken. Ni in CHCl₃ layer is stripped with 0.5*N* HCl, titrated with EDTA at pH ~10 (NH₄Cl/NH₄OH) using murexide indicator.

^fAt pH 5–6 (NaAc/HAc) both Al and Cd form EDTA complex. At this pH, however, Al does not form any xanthate complex; Cd forms extractable xanthate.

^gThe end-point of EDTA-Cd titration has an orange tinge. No vanadium was found to be present in HNO₃ solution (FeCl₃ + DMG test).

NOTE

This quick extractive method of separation together with easy and accurate titrimetric estimation of cadmium may be used in routine analysis of cadmium in binary mixtures with other ions in technological laboratories. Besides, the method may also be practised in academic concerns to make the students conversant with easy, quick and economic extractive method of qualitative and quantitative analysis of cadmium.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.K.C.) expresses his grate-

fulness to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the sanction of a Minor Research Grant for carrying out research works.

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